

Uncovering relationality from transactional data using dynamic graphs: case study from activation labour market policy in Italy.

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Giampaolo Montaletti graduated in Economics from the University of Bologna and is a Visiting Research Fellow at Northumbria University. He has long experience in the implementation of public policies, including work on a number of programs funded by the Italian Government and the European Commission for active labor policies (ALMP) and training. He has participated in the development of strategic frameworks as well as the design and construction of new policy instruments and has significant experience in statistical analysis. His current interests concern the theoretical and experimental design and evaluation of public policies.

Abstract

The paper aims to show how "transactional" administrative data existing in public administration archives can be used to discover relational aspects of the labor market and active policy programmes. A statistical methodology is outlined and illustrated in the context of a case study concerning the professional transitions of residents in the area of the Milan Public Employment Center (CPI Milan). The analysis makes use of the administrative data of the Mandatory Communications from the SISTAL 2.0 archives. The data were remodeled using network diagrams to identify groups of professions between which job transitions most often occur. The methods are then used to offer an interpretation of the impact of the internship on professional mobility.

Keywords

- Administrative data
- Mandatory communications
- SISTAL 2.0
- Graph analytics
- Labor market statistics
- Active labor policies (ALMP)

- Apprenticeship
- Relational services

Work transitions and labor policies

The evaluation of labor policies has been developed in Italy with the use of statistical analysis methods based on a principle of linearity and proportionality of the result with respect to the action.

Some active employment policy programs (ALMP) began with a significant relational orientation and personalization of support to the person, but “the policy thrust has moved from a position of relational services to a more transactional basis” (Montaletti, et al. 2022) with greater emphasis on “cost standardization which is presented as a ‘simplification’, resulting in the commodification of actions so that personalization is no longer really taking place” (Montaletti, et al. 2022). Active labor market policies are mainly implemented with pay-for-performance systems. Many scholars have highlighted the emergence of cherry picking phenomena (Lowe and Wilson 2017; Pastore, 2020) and gaming (Scarano, 2023).

The main evaluation method, favored by the use of mandatory communications (Strano et al. 2008) and by the continuous availability of updates to the administrative datasets, presupposes that the employment contracts stipulated after the implementation of an active political action can be a consequence (a result) attributable to the policy itself.

The evaluation is thus entrusted to the succession of events and has become consolidated as the main tool for monitoring and operational evaluation of the programmes; for example, see the reports relating to the GOL program (ANPAL 2024).

Many environmental and qualitative variables influence both the job search process and its outcome. In parallel with the development of analyzes on the effectiveness of policies in terms of placement, a growing number of analyzes emphasize the mismatch between supply and demand, such as the periodic Excelsior survey (Unioncamere 2025), without the two lines of research intersecting.

In the past a counterfactual analysis, making use of the same data from the Mandatory Communications (Colombo et al. 2015), as been performed, showing that relocation rates are very different for different groups of workers and not depending on the design of policy; the proportionality between resources and result does not appear to be confirmed empirically.

The objective of the analysis tools proposed and used in this paper is to reintroduce the complexity that the labor market presents at a local level among the policy evaluation factors, to evaluate how this complexity actually influences the outcomes of the policies. The case relating to transitions in the Milan public

employment service area and the role of the internship illustrate the analytical problems and potential results of the proposed approach.

Literature review

In parallel with the spread of complexity theories over the last twenty years, many efforts have been made in many disciplines to represent and, when possible, "model the real world... to help inform our actions" (Mowles, 2021).

In the social sciences, several modeling exercises have been developed to describe complex systems that show adaptability and dynamic evolution: "Those collective wholes that do not evolve and do not learn are complex systems; those that do are complex adaptive systems (CAS)." (Youngman et al., 2014).

The analysis spans across different fields and topics.

The spread of information systems and social networks has made data available that can be modeled with the use of graph-based representations (Arnaboldi et al., 2015) as a method for exploring relationship networks (Kingan, 2022). Sociology has adopted graphs to explore the dynamic evolution of relationships: "Relationships emerge, evolve, decline, end, begin again, change and take on different qualities." (Bidart et al., 2020). Several statistical tools, often based on exponential regression models (ERGM), have been developed to describe network dynamics (Krivitsky, 2023) and represent the evolution (in terms of formation and dissolution) of structural changes in relationships: "a dynamic network is one whose entire structure varies with respect to time" (Crane 2018).

Egocentric networks have been used to explore the role of racial disparity in the spread of HIV in the United States (Krivitsky and Morris 2017). The Relevant Event Framework has been used to model communication behavior in emergency contexts (Butts, 2008). A variable coefficient exponential random graph model (VCERGM) has been used to track the evolution of co-voting networks in the US Senate (Lee et al 2020). In recent times, a wide variety of deep learning methods have been developed to capture anomalies (Ma 2021). Anomaly detection is also widely used as a tool to identify change points in the structure of dynamic networks (Kandanaarachchi and Hyndman 2024).

As regards the analysis of the labor market, several scholars have made use of administrative databases to analyze the evolution of relations in the labor market.

The overall graph of employer-employee relations in Finland (LFN) was used to identify companies with high growth potential (Guerrero Axtell, 2013).

In Austria, social security archives were processed with network analysis tools to identify endogenous labor markets revealed by professional mobility flows. The effects on employment following local labor demand shocks and mobility responses to competition from imports from China and Eastern Europe were analysed. (Nimczik, 2017)

A similar analysis on the Austrian labor market was carried out on administrative registers for the private sector employment universe, exploring the impact of networks formed by former work colleagues in the process of finding a new job (Saygin [et.al](#) 2014).

Using social security data in France, a network was reconstructed that tracks the work trajectories of French workers between 2003 and 2015. In this network, transitions from one occupation to another are interpreted as a proxy for the proximity of skills required by different professions (Joyez and Laffineur, 2022).

An employer-worker dataset was reconstructed with Belgian data on company-to-company sales relationships, used to evaluate the mobility of workers across their current employers' buyer or supplier networks (Komatsu Dhyneba, 2023).

Employment transitions in the United States between 2010 and 2017 were used to develop a graph-based model that analyzes how workers move through an empirically derived occupational mobility network in response to automation scenarios (del Rio-Chanona, 2021).

Using a collection of data from Statistic Denmark for the years 2000–2007, a group of scholars (Toubøl et al., 2013) developed the MONECA algorithm (Mobility Network Clustering Algorithm) which allows the identification of clusters of professions based on worker transitions. The use of network analysis allows for a data-driven definition of what a market segment is based on direct observation of mobility between job positions (Toubøl et al., 2013). This algorithm is used in this paper for the same purposes.

Despite the wide availability of administrative methods and datasets, the evaluation practices of active labor market policies (ALMP) in Italy remain static (Montaletti et al 2022).

It is true that there is widespread consensus on the limits of modeling (of any kind) in the social sciences, as one complexity scholar observes: “It is impossible to have a perfect model of a complex system. This is not due to some inadequacy in our modeling techniques, but a result of the meaning of the notions “model” and “complex”. There will always be a gap between the two. This gap should serve as a creative impulse that continually challenges us to transform our models, not as a reason to give up” (Cilliers, 2001). The author shares this approach and tries to offer an application, seeking "feedback from the world that tells us something about the adequacy of our models" (Cilliers, 2001).

A method for detecting transitions

Mandatory communications allow you to evaluate and count people's transitions on the market.

By ordering the different employment contracts of a person along the timeline, it is possible to observe the transitions from one profession to another and from one employer to another.

We focus on completed work transitions (i.e. on the periods of time between the conclusion of a contract and the start of the next one), and we can observe several possible variations that concern multiple dimensions that change at the end of a transition:

- the professional dimension (what work I do);
- the contractual dimension (duration, remuneration, full time or part time, individual benefits...)
- the organizational dimension (in which company, in which town, in which industrial sector)

The set of these factors substantially qualifies every transition and every career, that is to say every succession of transitions.

In this work we focus on professional transitions, i.e. the transition from one profession to another, which occupy a good part of analysis activities on the mismatch and on the development of skills.

For the purposes of this work, the analysis takes place on a portion of the Lombardy region (the Milan PES) with the aim of evaluating the work transitions of people living in that area in the years 2021–2022–2023. The source used is the SISTAL2 database (March 2024 extraction), built through an in-depth series of quality controls on mandatory administrative communications. The procedure reconstructs the succession of events (starts, terminations, extensions and transformations) in a table of employment relationships, where each row represents a contractual relationship between a person and an employer. The database is used anonymously with the kind permission of the Metropolitan City of Milan, but the conclusions drawn in this work are the sole responsibility of the author.

Only contracts started from January 1, 2021 onwards will be treated for the analysis. Transitions from work to non-work and vice versa are not covered, as they are "open" or not concluded transitions according to the definition we use, even if the extension to these transitions is a natural evolution of the proposed methodologies.

The professions used are those of the ISTAT profession classifications (ISTAT 2021) in the third digit of the positional code. For brevity, the descriptions have been summarized in three-word graphic representations, while for some tables the complete descriptions have been tuned to 45 characters. The classification includes 130 different professions.

From the database it is possible to compile a transition matrix, which shows the 130 professions on the rows and columns and in each cell the movement from the profession in the row to the one in the column which we can represent with a mobility graph.

The transition matrix has on the diagonal all the contract changes that see the same person returning to work with the same contractual qualification. For our purposes of analyzing inter-professional mobility we do not currently consider the two categories of transitions on the diagonal, which are also of some interest for the purposes of evaluating labor policies:

- the transitions which see the worker reiterate the contract with the same employer (and therefore in the same sector, often with the same contractual and organizational conditions). In our Milan PES matrix, this represents approximately 40% of the total transitions detected.
- the transitions which involve a change in the employer but not in the profession carried out, account for approximately 30% of the total transitions.

The matrix is also used as a calculation basis by the MONECA algorithm (Toubøl et al. 2017). In a dense network like the one depicted in Figure 1, where almost all nodes are connected, it is difficult to identify and make sense of the structure. To facilitate the reading of the graph, we try to identify nodes that are closely connected to each other. The identification of cohesive and non-overlapping subgroups allows us to identify markets and professional groups.

Conventional network analysis concepts that base clustering on cliques are problematic because they produce overlapping cluster solutions. MONECA is a clustering algorithm that clusters based on weighted ties. In our case the weight that determines proximity is the number of transitions between nodes.

The processing and graphic representations are developed in R (R Core Team, 2024) using the Qgraph (Epskamp et al., 2012), Igraph (Csardi Nepusz, 2024) and Ggraph (Pedersen T, 2024) libraries. The MONECA library (Grau, 2019) was also used, with some adaptations and updates by the author.

A case: the transitions of residents in the CPI of Milan and the role of the internship

The complexity of the market and its representation

In our case, the transitions concluded (contract changes) in three years were approximately 858,487, and involved 226,064 different workers and 93,608 different employers.

This is a transition process that involves many different parties.

The graph representing the transitions is presented in Figure 1.

The graph represents a profession for each (circular) node and the incoming and outgoing arrows represent the transitions to and from that profession with respect to the others.

The representation highlights the complexity of the labor market, and although the direction and thickness of each arrow tries to highlight which transitions are the most frequently followed, the representation remains difficult to understand.

Figure 1.

However, we can observe some characteristics of the graph:

- Some professions are more central than others, which means that they have a greater level of interchange between themselves and between themselves and others. Some professions constitute real hubs with respect to the overall mobility of the market.
- The probability of moving from one profession to another (of moving from one node to another) can be estimated by the frequency with which one exits towards the arrival node compared to the overall exit from that node. That is to say that the probability of moving from low-skilled professions (for example cleaning services) to high-skilled professions (for example company management) can be

estimated from the ratio between those who move from one position to another and all those leaving the cleaning profession towards all other professions. The probability of transition does not only depend on the individual condition, but also on the continuous evolution of the relationships that each profession has with all the others. In other words, the complexity of the system determines changes in the probability of transition even if workers and employers do not change their individual positions and contracts.

- The more frequent transition from some professions to others is made possible by the similarity of skills that are required to carry out the two professions. A high exchange of people between different professions therefore allows us to identify professional clusters. This approach offers us the possibility of identifying the spaces closest to individual career evolution, without the paths being deterministic: to reach the same professional group there are different possible paths, some of which are more probable, others less so, some which require greater adaptation of skills, and therefore greater times and costs than others, with the caveat that the market shows emerging trends which are subject to change. These changes are also dictated by external conditions: the spread of technologies, the pandemic, wars, are examples of factors that have influenced transitions and the evolution of their probability.

The identification of groups of professions in the market.

To make the market dynamics more legible, we identified groups of professions that have more frequent transitions within the same group with the MONECA algorithm (Toubøl et al. 2017).

The algorithm was applied to all transitions over the three-year period at a regional level, but figure 2 only shows the graph for workers domiciled in the CPI area of Milan.

Figure 2 - Professional groups identified based on transitions.

services to people	156.676	72	59,2	33,9	27,9	63
industrial	104.266	62	65,9	29,2	31,6	51
trade	101.666	59	63,0	31,8	29,5	46
education	84.352	159	63,5	44,9	32,6	70
others	82.430	2	84,0	75,9	55,5	28
sale	71.345	43	66,0	43,6	31,2	48
management	70.474	181	37,3	16,2	20,9	35
building	60.032	68	69,1	39,4	30,2	53
Public admin	55.292	184	38,6	18,0	18,4	51
Entertainment	34.083	2	91,2	72,2	60,0	26
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STEM	24.867	212	41,8	18,5	22,7	62
finance	22.984	172	41,5	18,6	22,5	41
fashion	17.470	4	79,1	60,5	47,5	33
logistics	13.897	91	58,9	35,8	25,8	47
food	7.417	61	64,6	27,1	27,6	48
agriculture	5.425	85	64,0	33,2	23,8	75

The table shows the presence of groups characterized by contracts with a short median duration and a high percentage of completed exit transitions; among these completed transitions there is a strong presence of returns to the same profession that they left and a strong percentage of returns with a duration equal to or less than 8 days. The 8-day measurement allows us to evaluate which transitions generate unemployment in the strict sense: under 8 days you are not entitled to receive benefits linked to the state of unemployment, nor, if interviewed during the labor force survey, are you considered unemployed (you are employed if you have carried out at least one paid hour of work in the seven days prior to the interview).

Employers of professional groups linked to tourism (hotels and restaurants), culture, entertainment and fashion use short but recurring contracts. On the other hand, we note the scientific and technical professions (STEM) and those related to management, finance and education which have longer median transition times and contracts with a median duration close to or greater than 180 days.

Professional groups and mobility

For each professional group it is possible to identify mobility to and from the group, identifying which professions contribute to the growth (or decrease of the group) and towards which other groups it contributes through outgoing transitions.

By way of example, table 2 shows the first 10 professions that are practiced after leaving the group of professions in hotels and restaurants, which are all leaving the profession of shopkeepers and employees in catering activities (mainly waiters).

Table 2: Transitions leaving the hotel and restaurant group, top 10 subsequent professions

outgoing profession	subsequent profession	transitions
Operators and employees in catering activities	Unqualified staff in cleaning services	4066
Operators and employees in catering activities	Sales people	3746
Operators and employees in catering activities	Unqualified personnel responsible for moving	1883
Operators and employees in catering activities	Craftsmen and specialized workers responsible for cleaning	920
Operators and employees in catering activities	Reception and information staff of the c	888
Operators and employees in catering activities	Secretarial and general affairs staff	750
Operators and employees in catering activities	Logistics administrative management personnel	626
Operators and employees in catering activities	Specialists in expressive artistic disciplines	578
Operators and employees in catering activities	Production process management technicians	576
Operators and employees in catering activities	Unqualified personnel assigned to kitchen services	500

Similarly, in Table 3 we can see which are the main professions that contribute to the dynamics of the group as a point of arrival.

Table 3: Transitions entering the hotel and restaurant group, top 10 previous professions

previous profession	entry_profession	transitions
Unqualified staff in cleaning services	Operators and employees in catering activities	5136
Sales people	Operators and employees in catering activities	3286

Unqualified personnel responsible for moving	Operators and employees in catering activities	2237
Craftsmen and specialized workers responsible for cleaning	Operators and employees in catering activities	1190
Reception and information staff of the c	Operators and employees in catering activities	752
Logistics administrative management personnel	Operators and employees in catering activities	671
Specialists in expressive artistic disciplines	Operators and employees in catering activities	645
Secretarial and general affairs staff	Operators and employees in catering activities	589
Unqualified personnel assigned to kitchen services	Operators and employees in catering activities	543
Unqualified personnel assigned to domes services	Operators and employees in catering activities	535

The overall budget for the three-year period in question is 152,083 incoming transitions and 151,759 outgoing transitions.

The balance of this great mobility is just 324 units.

Transitions from internship to professional group

Internships are communicated via the COB system and we can track transitions from internship to professional group.

Table 4: Internship as a provenance in transitions towards professional groups

professional arrival group	number of transitions	percentage of the total transitions arriving in the group	median distance in days from the end of the internship
management	5988	22.0	3.0
Public admin	4254	18.1	3.0
finance	1603	16.3	4.0
STEM	1308	12.2	2.0
trade	3950	6.3	3.0
agriculture	168	5.4	31.0
sale	2138	4.6	11.0

food	199	4.1	14.5
industrial	1559	2.3	8.5
fashion	295	2.1	5.0
Hotel and rest.	1920	1.3	10.0
education	521	0.9	11.0
service people	823	0.9	23.0
others	388	0.6	3.0
logistics	54	0.6	24.0
culture	754	0.5	3.0
Entertainment	117	0.4	12.0
building	139	0.3	19.0

Table 4 shows how the internship has taken on a weight in the transitions of groups with medium-high skills, such as management professions (many computer scientists are also found in the group), in finance, in Public Administration and regulations, which includes some legal professions, in STEM professions (engineers, scientists, etc...). These are groups which, as we have seen previously, do not have a particularly high weight among new hires, but which have longer contracts and longer selection times on average. In a certain sense, the internship constitutes a time of transition, given its nature as a training event subject to public regulation, conceived as a policy that facilitates the job placement of younger people.

Where the percentages of incoming internships are high, the median times from the end of the internship are very short. The data shows that this is often a training period added to formal study paths (degrees and high school qualifications).

Implications for labor policies

Active labor market policies usually intervene in open transitions, i.e. when people are looking for their first or subsequent job.

The use of the internship as an example in this paper allowed us to maintain the analysis within the SISTAL2 data space without resorting to further information on active policies and data residing in other management systems.

However, it is possible, similarly to what was seen for the internship, to evaluate which training and employment policies intersect the transitions, so as to estimate their weight in the development of individual careers within the professional families that are gradually formed in the market dynamics.

Internship is a widely adopted policy for introducing young people into professional groups with a high knowledge content. It is a question of understanding whether this adoption is actually functional in

strengthening the learning processes of the profession, or whether it does not delay entry into the profession at adequate levels of remuneration and social protection.

The volatility of the characteristics of transitions, which depends over time on changing conditions external to the market and the emergence of internal mobility processes, forces us to rethink the standardization of people support processes that employment services have undergone over the years.

Tools such as internships are general purpose ones, which can be directly adapted by employers in their contents and methods of implementation. Specific training and support actions for the unemployed in the transition based on standard costs and performance catalogs (Italian Gov. 2021) have less flexibility and suffer from variable effectiveness as the conditions of job demand vary.

The question arises whether in a dynamic market it is necessary to bring employment services back to their dimension of relational services (Smith 2024), that is to say paths that are defined in a dialogue between employment services workers and the supported persons. Services could grow in the construction of an accompanying relationship that takes into account both people's needs and the constant evolutions of the local market and the relationship system.

Equally urgent is the improvement of analysis and evaluation methods. When ALMP programs are organized as results-based services, accountability is designed according to the results of the procedures themselves. The complex reality of labor markets makes this accountability-lead design less effective .

In complex environments the outcome is a systemic and emergent property: “outcomes are shaped by interdependent and dynamically interacting factors well beyond the individual or organizational boundary that cannot be completely separated into components” (French et al., 2023).

This definition of outcome as an emergent property across organizational boundaries opens up further research questions: “How can we ensure that addressing complexity does not lead to a de-emphasis, or even worse, a deficit of accountability? ... A pragmatic goal might therefore be to determine a model of accountability that is a workable compromise in both democratic and functional terms.” (French et al., 2023). Responding to this challenge, graph analysis to represent the evolution of relationships between the actors involved in a labor policy program, using administrative data sets, can be used in a functional evaluation process, which highlights the role of the system of relationships in determining the employment outcomes of active policy instruments.

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